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EXPRESSION OF CONDITIONAL SEMANTICS IN SIMPLE SENTENCES IN THE AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGE

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ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ УСЛОВНОЙ СЕМАНТИКИ ПРОСТЫМИ ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЯМИ НА АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Abstract.

In the Azerbaijani language, the condition sets up a separate functional-semantic field. The analysis of simple sentences in the peripheral zone of the field of functional-semantic conditionality is of special interest. The study deals with the analysis of the meaning of the condition the has implicitly been expressed in simple sentences on the basis of examples. In the Azerbaijani language, the main means of expressing conditionality are conditional clauses. Nevertheless, simple sentences are one of the means for expressing the conditional meaning in the Azerbaijani language. In traditional linguistics, the study of conditional semantics in simple sentences has often been neglected by researchers. Lack of linguistic researching in this direction increases the relevance of the topic. In simple sentences, the conditional meaning is expressed with the help of various methods. In the article, some of these means of expression are thoroughly analyzed. The non-finite forms of the verb are also analyzed as means of expressing conditional semantics. In order to justify our opinion, necessary examples and comments on these examples are included in the article. The analysis showed that conditional semantics are not directly expressed in these sentences and when these types of constructions are converted into a complex sentence, the conditional meaning is more clearly visible.

Аннотация.

В азербайджанском языке условие представляет собой отдельное функционально-семантическое поле. Особый интерес представляет анализ простых предложений в периферийной зоне поля функционально-семантической условности. Темой исследования является анализ значения условия, имплицитно выраженного в простых предложениях, на основе примеров. Основным средством выражения условного значения в азербайджанском языке являются условные предложения. Тем не менее, простые предложения являются одним из средств выражения условного значения в азербайджанском языке. В традиционной лингвистике изучение условной семантики простых предложений часто игнорируется исследователями. Отсутствие лингвистических исследований в этом направлении повышает актуальность темы. В простых предложениях условное значение выражается с помощью различных средств. В статье подробно анализируются некоторые из этих средств выразительности. Неклассифицированные формы глагола также включены в анализ как средства выражения условной семантики. Для обоснования нашего мнения в статье приведены необходимые примеры и комментарии к этим примерам. Анализ показал, что условная семантика в этих предложениях непосредственно не выражена, а при преобразовании данных типов конструкций в сложноподчиненное предложение условный смысл проявляется более отчетливо.

Key words: *the Azerbaijani language, conditionality, functional-semantic conditional field, conditional constructions, simple sentence*

Ключевые слова: *азербайджанский язык, условность, функционально-семантическое условное поле, условные конструкции, простое предложение*

Today, in linguistics, a field approach is used to analyze different language phenomena. So what is the concept of functional-semantic field? A.V.Bondarko identifies the functional-semantic field as “a two-way (content - formal) union formed by the grammatical (morphological and syntactic) means of a certain language and the lexical, lexical-grammatical and word-creative elements of the same semantic field associated with them”. [13, p.40]. The understanding of

the objective world that surrounds us is often associated with the concept of condition. In the language, the presence of a number of language tools in the conditionality and the presence of a system in which they are combined according to their semantic-functional characteristics allows to analyze the condition as a functional-semantic field. The issue of structuring the center of the

field of functional-semantic conditionality and the constituents that make up this field is certainly of interest in the Azerbaijani language.

Each language has its unique field model, that is, the field of conditionality is formed in different languages through the help of different linguistic means. Thus, the field of conditionality in language consists of tools belonging to different levels of the language with conditional semantics. All of them serve the same semantic function - the expression of conditional meaning in language. Note that these means of expression sometimes together and sometimes separately create conditional semantics. These means of expression belonging to all levels of the language, of course, do not express this meaning equally. Therefore, sentences with conditional semantics have different positions in the field of functional-semantic conditionality. In other words, some language units are specialized, while others depend on context and situation. Thus, some of the field's constituents are located in the core and others in the periphery. Conditional meaning is firstly expressed by the affix *-sa / -sə* as an indicator of the conditional form of the verb in the Azerbaijani language. However, contextual-situational means in the language also play an important role in order to express conditional semantics. Constructions with dual semantics are in the near periphery of the field, and constructions with fewer signs of the condition take place in the far periphery. Thus, it is possible to group various means belonging to the far periphery of the field of functional-semantic conditionality in the Azerbaijani language. Additional shades of meaning arise when these tools express conditional meaning.

One of the most convenient constructions for conveying ideas clearly and concisely in speech are simple sentences. In many languages, simple sentences expressing conditional semantics constitute the far periphery of the domain. Because these sentences, which form the periphery of the field of functional-semantic conditionality, are not as effective as other elements in the expression of conditional meaning. However, here the word or phrase expressing conditional semantics only indicates the condition, gets close to it. Thus, in simple sentences, the condition can be expressed only from the semantic side, and from the formal point of view, it does not meet the requirements of conditionality [4, p.10] Conditional semantics in simple sentences manifests itself more secretly, and many linguistic facts help it in this work.

In the language the conditional meaning can also be expressed by lexical means. They are used in simple sentences and perform the function of grammatical indicators of conditionality and express different shades of meaning of conditionality. We believe that such combinations as *under normal conditions, in another place or another time, otherwise (... in case), otherwise* are like this:

Başqa yerdə ağzınızdan söz qaçırmayasız ha! – You can't miss a word anywhere else! [5, p.136] Həqiqət olmadığı halda mənim haqqımda yazılanlara əhəmiyyət vermərəm. – I don't care what is written about me unless it's the truth [colloquial speech].

With the help of the lexical means mentioned in the above sentences, the meaning of the condition is secretly expressed. That is, these lexical tools used in a simple sentence express the conditional semantics

indirectly, not directly. For example, it is possible to transform the first sentence into the form *"If there is another place, you won't miss a word."*

In some cases, it is possible to see that adjectives define nouns and condition the execution of the action in the sentence. In this case, in addition to having a defining function, the adjective also contains nuances of distinction and condition. For example: *Ah, knyaz, bilirsiniz ki, namuslu adam heç vaxt bu dərəcədə alçaqlıq eləməz! – Ah, Kniaz, you know that an honest man would never commit such a disgrace!* [6, p.237] The meaning of the condition is more clearly visible when the mentioned sentence is converted into a complex sentence: *Namuslu adam olsa, heç vaxt bu dərəcədə alçaqlıq eləməz! – If he is an honest person, he would never commit such a disgrace!*

One of the constituents of the periphery of the field of functional-semantic conditionality is the suffix *-siz⁴*. If you transform the simple sentences with these suffixes in the appropriate way, the shades of the condition become clearer in them:

Kənddə bir toy, bir məclis onsuz keçmirdi. – In the village, a wedding, a party was not complete without him [8, p.154]. Təqsirsiz heç kəsi aparmazlar. – They don't take anyone who is innocent [3, p.264].

Of course, the conditional meaning is not very prominent in these sentences either. If these sentences are converted into conditional clauses, the conditional meaning will be more prominent. For example, *"Kənddə o olmasa, bir toy və məclis keçmirdi – If he is not in the village, no wedding or party did not take place"*. In other words, "he" must be present for the "meeting to take place". Otherwise, the meeting will not take place.

One of the main ways to express conditional semantics in simple sentences are the non-finite forms of the verb. In Azerbaijani linguistics, it is known that the non-finite forms of verbs do not change according to person and quantity and therefore often attract the attention of linguists. In the literature of linguistics, there has not been a unified view of the non-finite forms of the verb. These constructions are interpreted differently by linguists: some analyze them in a simple sentence system, others as an aspect of some kind of complex sentence. Currently, sentences with these verb forms are considered simple sentences in Azerbaijani linguistics. The non-finite forms of the verb are formed by adding certain suffixes to the root or base of the verb. In Azerbaijani linguistics, infinitives, verb adjectives, and verb conjunctions belong to the non-finite forms of the verb.

Conditional semantics in a simple sentence is created through an infinitive. Let's pay attention to the following sentences:

Öz bədbəxtliyinlə barışmaq, bəlkə də, səni ən bədbəxt yox, nisbətən xoşbəxt edir – Reconciling with your unhappiness makes you relatively happy, not the most unhappy... [5, p.104] O işdən ötrü, xanım, dua yazmaq yaramaz – Because of that work, madam, it is not enough to write a prayer [8, p.39].

We can think of this sentence as *"Ma'am, if you write a prayer for that job, it won't work."* In this sentence, of course, the news should be expressed in the future tense. If the news is processed in the past tense, then it will not be possible to convert the condition into a conditional clause. Because it is difficult to talk about the condition of an already finished action.

We can also see the conditional content in the sentences with the verbal adjectives from the non-finite forms of the verb. For example:

Mənə qulaq asmayan xeyir tapmaz, bala – Who does not listen to me will not do well [8, p.87]. Şəxsiyyət, vicdan azadlığı olmayan yerdə hansı həyatdan danışmaq olar? – What kind of life can we talk about where there is no freedom of personality and conscience? [6, p.238] Sevənlər bitərəf adamlar kimi danışa bilməzlər – Lovers cannot speak like neutral people [6, p.47].

It is true that the conditional meaning in these sentences is not as prominent as in complex sentences. If in the first parts of the above sentences make certain changes, structurally combined simple sentences will have conditional shades due to changes in their structure.

One of the non-finite forms of the verb in the Azerbaijani language is the verb conjugation. Verb conjugation in Azerbaijani language has quite a lot of morphological indicators. It is known that verb conjugation in the language explain the predicate in a sentence in different ways. Verb conjugation also implicitly state the condition of the predicate. In all cases, expressing the conditional meaning is not the main function of such sentences, but a derivative function. That is, in such sentences, the first meaning expressed by the verb conjugation suffixes is the main one, while the conditional meaning is considered derivative. Morphological indicators of the verb conjugation *-madan², -anda², -mamis², -digca⁴, -ınca⁴* serve to create a certain shade of condition in the sentence:

Ona yedikcə çörək verərəm, geydikcə paltar verərəm. – I will give him bread as he eats, and clothes as he wears [7, p.448]. Ancaq müharibə olanda sahibi bu möcüzəli atı minir – However, when there is a war, the owner rides this wonderful horse [10, p.35]. Ağsa, səbr eylə, hələ vaxta var və bizə növbə yetişməmiş biletlər verməzlər – Sir, be patient, there is still time and they won't give us tickets before the line is up [7, p.128]. Ona görə də onun sözünün, vədələrini dürüst olmasını yaqin eləməyincə onları kənd seçkisinə yavuş qoymaq olmaz – Therefore, they should not be allowed to participate in the village election until we make sure that their words and promises are honest [8, p.466].

As can be seen from the examples, verb conjugations formed with the help of these suffixes first indicate time. We know that verb conjunctions not only indicate the time of execution of the main verb in the sentence, but also the manner, reason, situation and duration. However, we can see that the verb bindings, which we claim to have a conditional meaning, mostly determine the tense of the main verb in those sentences. This is also proved by the presence of the time meaning in the mentioned sentences along with the conditional meaning. When these constructions turn into conditional clauses, the conditional meaning becomes more prominent. As can be seen, verb conjugation suffixes are widely used as indicators of conditional semantics in simple sentences. The fact that verb

conjugations have an independent subject also makes it easier to turn them into complex sentences.

The relevance of simple sentences to the field of functional-semantic conditionality can be determined by their transformation into complex sentences. As a result of simple structure sentences becoming complex sentence structure again, conditional content shows itself more clearly. In this case, the complete non-change of the meaning is due to the fact that the transformation event does not affect the general meaning of the sentence. Thus, by turning a simple sentence into a complex sentence, it is possible to determine how semantically its components are related to each other.

The analysis showed that these mentioned tools play an important role in implicitly expressing conditional semantics in simple sentences. We should note that the expression of the meaning of the condition in simple sentences is mainly stylistic. In the Azerbaijani language, the condition can be expressed with its full meaning only in complex sentences. Therefore, the means of expression mentioned in the article constitute the far periphery of the field of functional-semantic conventionality.

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